

Investigation of the microwave assisted pultrusion and resin transfer moulding (RTM) process with thermoplastic resin and cure monitoring

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Introduction

Fiber reinforced composites are widely used in transport and sports industries. The major benefit of composites is that these materials are about 30 to 40% lighter than metal parts having comparable properties. Nowadays thermoset resins are mainly used for composites, because the uncured polymer resins have a low viscosity for a good infiltration of the fibers and short cycle times. Nevertheless, they cannot be easily recycled. Now, new reactive polymer resins like Elium® are commercially available, which cure like thermoset resins but can be recycled as thermoplastic materials giving the possibility of subsequent shaping etc¹ with processing methods for thermoplastics. The viscosity of these new resins are low enough to ensure the necessary good infiltration of fibers, too.

Recotrans project aims to enhance the processing of the reactive thermoplastic composites for transport applications. Therefore one of our main objective is to optimize the curing conditions for pultrusion and resin transfer moulding (RTM), by employing advanced technologies such as microwave assisted curing and intelligent reaction monitoring.

It has been shown that the electrical resistance of a resin is directly related to the resin's viscosity and T_g ⁶. Based on this observation and experimenting with several resins, Synthesites developed a proprietary technology for the online estimation of the development of the Glass Transition (T_g) temperature and/or of the degree of cure valid not only in the laboratory but also during composites production. This technology has been already applied successfully to thermoset-based composites manufacturing in automotive, wind turbine blades, and aerospace while in reactive thermoplastics it was used only in lab-scale trials. Based on this principle that has been widely proven in practice, the resistivity of a resin was directly related to its viscosity while the T_g temperature can be estimated online using Synthesites proprietary algorithms via the Online Resin State (ORS) module. This online estimation technique was extended successfully for the specific acrylic resin that is being used in the Recotrans project. The ORS module was initially developed for isothermal cure cycles and was further extended to deal with highly non-isothermal conditions i.e. high exothermic polymerization reactions with long cooling stages. For reactive thermoplastic resins the resistance correlates with the residual of the monomer which corresponds to the degree of conversion.

Dielectric Characterization

We measure the dielectric function of the Elium® resin with hardener at the frequency of 2.45GHz as a function of temperature with the cavity perturbation method (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Measurement equipment for measuring the dielectric function

From the frequency shift from the empty and loaded cavity and the corresponding reduction of the quality factor the real and imaginary part of the dielectric function can be determined. In Figure 2 the real and imaginary part of the dielectric function of Elium® with 1.5 mass % of curing agent is shown at 2.45 GHz as a function of temperature.

Figure 2: Dielectric function for Elium® with 1.5% curing agent at 2.45 GHz

Elium® shows a high real part and a medium imaginary part of the dielectric function at room temperature. With increasing temperature both parts of the dielectric function of the Elium® resin drops because it starts to polymerize in these conditions until 100°C where it is completely polymerized.

Microwave assisted pultrusion

Pultrusion is the only continuous process for production of composite structural components with constant cross-sectional area. The curing time of the resin limits the pultrusion speed, which significantly influences the cost of production. The pulling speed for reactive thermoplastic Elium® resin can be increased by microwave-assisted pultrusion (MAP) resulting in more profitable pultrusion production. In microwave assisted pultrusion a microwave-transparent die or insert mostly made of ceramic is added before the classical metal die^{2 3 4}.

In Figure 3 a sketch of the microwave assisted pultrusion die is shown for a rod of diameter 16 mm. The die consists of a ceramic part, which is placed at the end of a tapered waveguide. The geometry and the dimensions of the ceramic part were designed that the electric field along the cross section of the rod is homogenous. The length of the microwave die is about 10 cm (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Sketch of the microwave pultrusion die

To provide better understanding of the microwave assisted pultrusion process for Elium® we investigate the temperature development and the curing in the pultrusion die with and without microwave assistance for different process parameters. For these investigations, a fiber optical temperature sensor was fed together with the glass fibers in the pultrusion die (Figure 4) and the temperature was measured in the pultruded rod. The fiber optical temperature sensor had a length of about 150 cm. When the optical fiber was completely drawn in it was cut off.

Figure 4: Entrance of the pultrusion die with glass fibers and the fiber optical temperature sensor

In Figure 5, the temperature development of the curing rod is shown with and without microwaves as it is pultruded in the pultrusion die.

The comparison of the both graphs shows the microwave effect. In case of a pultrusion without microwave the temperature increases uniformly to maximum of about 152°C after 118 cm in the pultrusion die. The additional microwave energy causes a sharp increase of the temperature from room temperature to about 70°C in the first 10 cm of the die, following a moderate increase in the conventional heated die to a maximum of 162°C already after 100 cm. These effects lead to an improvement of the pulling speed by about 50% and reduction of the pulling force of about 50%.

Figure 5: Temperature distribution of the rod during pultrusion

Microwave assisted resin transfer moulding (RTM)

RTM process is used in many cases to produce structural composite parts with complex geometries. Metal moulds are used for high volume production and cycle times are an obstacle to high volume RTM. Cycle times are dictated by thermal quench near the injection gate from cold resin entering the hot mould. Heat recovery by the mould, and coincident heating of the resin to initiate cure is necessary to complete the cycle.

Microwave preheating of the resin before injection reduces thermal quench. Since microwave heating is volumetric, low thermal conductivity resins can be heated uniformly and efficiently. In-line resin preheating has been developed and tested for its compatibility with high volume RTM^{5 6}.

The mould was made of aluminium with dimensions 280 mm wide and 380 mm long (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**). As prescribed by the automotive use case, carbon fiber mats of density 400 g/cm² and Elium® resin with benzoyl peroxide hardener were used. Two mats were inserted into the mould (pre-heated either at 80°C or 90°C) and the mould was closed up to a gap of approx. 5 mm between top of the mould and fibre mats. Through this gap the resin flows during injection and is simultaneously heated by microwaves. As soon as the mould is filled, the microwave is switched off and the mould is closed, and pressure is raised to 8 bar for the infiltration of the mats with the resin and curing. The microwave nozzle was sealed with a ceramic plate to prevent the resin from flowing into the microwave.

In the top tool, a durable sensor (DC sensor in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**, Right) was installed, flush mounted in the cavity to measure online the electrical resistance and temperature. The sensor was connected to the Optimold cure monitoring system as provided by Synthesites and the measurements were recorded in a PC through the Optiview data acquisition software.

Figure 6: Lab-scale unit for RTM with pre-heater

In Figure 7 four exemplaric trials at two mould temperatures (80°C and 90°C) with or without MW heating are shown.

Figure 7: Resistance (R) and Temperature (T) of the injections 6 and 7 with (mw6 and mw7) and without (ref6 and ref7) MW resin preheating

Figure 8: Resistance rate (dR) and Temperature (T) of the injections 6 and 7 with (mw6 and mw7) and without (ref6 and ref7) MW preheating.

The derivation of the resistance according to time can be used to define the end of the reaction so if threshold is set to 0.2 as denoted by yellow dashed line in the fig.8 the required curing times are shown for each case. The clear advantage of using the MW preheating is shown with a speed-up of 25% with respect to the specific temperature and 41% overall has been achieved (table 1).

Case	Processing time (min)	Speed-up (with respect ref6)	Speed-up (with respect ref6)
ref6	8.1		
Mw6	7.2	11%	11%
Ref7	6.4	21%	
Mw7	4.8	41%	21%

Table 2. Processing times and corresponding speed-up factors with respect to reference cases without MW (ref6 and ref7) and with MW preheating (mw6 and mw7), resp.

Conclusion

Microwave systems for pultrusion and RTM were developed and tested successfully for the acceleration of the reaction using a liquid reactive thermoplastic resin. For the pultrusion a microwave module was mounted in front in a conventional heated pultrusion die. The trials show that the microwave assistance speed up the curing resulting in a 50% faster pulling speed and a reduction of the pulling force of about 50%. Therefore with microwave assistance it is possible to run one pultrusion machine with two pultrusion dies and with higher speed, which reduces significantly the production costs.

Pre-heating the resin before injection in the RTM-mould reduces the curing time of about 25% at the same mould temperature and possible 41% overall. The pre-heater is easy to implement in the production of parts.

The DC-based cure monitoring system can provide in real-time the evolution of the reaction and as a result it allows for real-time quality and process control purposes during manufacturing. Its combination with microwave curing proved efficient and without any interfering effect of microwaves in the electric field of the sensor.

The next challenge in the Recotrans project is to extent, and demonstrate these advantages in the manufacturing of an automotive and train door panel that is currently under construction.

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